

Deliverable 8.3

ATLAS research outputs

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1 Executive summary

ATLAS has published a total of 462 research outputs in 2016-2020, and an additional 96 are currently in preparation. They consist of scientific articles (9%), data sets (17%), data products such as georeferenced maps (31%), and various “other” outputs (42%) that include project deliverables, cruise reports, presentations and posters (Figure 1). The latter are available at Zenodo¹, whereas scientific articles were published in peer-reviewed journals. The proportion of research outputs belonging to these four types is consistent with the research life cycle of a scientific consortium, where ideas are communicated and developed among peers through presentations and progress reports, leading to a relatively smaller number of articles that contribute to the wider scientific community. Also consistent with the life cycle of scientific knowledge, data sets and data products were published towards the end of the project, leading to data re-use and increased scientific impact beyond the life-time of the project. Together, data sets and products dominate the overall number of research outputs (48%). The present report provides a synthetic, but exhaustive overview of data sets and data products generated by ATLAS.

Figure 1. Number of ATLAS research outputs published from 2016-2020 as well as those still in preparation. Numbers are shown separately for peer-reviewed articles, data sets, data products such as georeferenced maps, and “other” research outputs such as project deliverables, cruise reports, presentations and posters.

Data sets - ATLAS published a total of 106 data sets in 2016-2020, and an additional 10 are currently in preparation. They were deposited in trusted archives and are currently available either in open access (69%), restricted access (16%) while under review, or under embargo (7%) for a period of 1-2 years (Figure 2). In the present report, we characterised data sets according to their data type, main research topic, parameters, methods, geographic region and access mode. Table 1 provides an overview of the different data types and research topics addressed by ATLAS data sets. Observations relevant for the study of biodiversity, biogeography, palaeoceanography and environmental conditions clearly dominate the portfolio, followed by observations related to human activity. A

¹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/atlas/>

number of modelling data sets were also published, particularly with regards to environmental conditions and paleoceanography. Data sets also provide expert’s assessments about habitat conservation, as well as experimental work on biological processes. Software code used to generate some data sets are also included in this overview. The complete inventory of ATLAS data sets is provided in Section 2, including the publication year, the name of the data repository and the URL pointing to each data set. The inventory is also available in a csv file attached to the present report.

ATLAS data sets by access mode

Figure 2. Number of ATLAS data sets published from 2016-2020 as well as those still in preparation. Numbers are shown separately according to their current access

Table 1. Summary of ATLAS data sets. Software code used to generate some data sets are also included in this category.

Data type	Research topic	parameter types	parameters	methods	regions	restricted access data sets	open access data sets
observations	ecotoxicology	1	6	1	1	0	1
	morphology	1	1	1	1	0	4
	species richness	1	1	1	1	0	1
	biodiversity & biogeography	1	36	6	8	8	11
	paleoceanography	3	8	2	3	9	10
	environmental conditions	3	30	5	4	1	13
	environmental processes	1	5	3	1	2	1
modelling	human activity	3	4	4	6	5	3
	connectivity	1	1	2	1	0	2
	biodiversity & biogeography	1	4	2	2	0	2
	environmental processes	1	3	3	3	0	3
	environmental conditions	3	18	3	5	0	10
	habitat suitability	1	14	2	2	0	2
	conservation	1	1	1	1	0	1
expert's assessment	paleoceanography	2	2	4	1	0	8
	conservation	1	2	2	4	3	3
experiments	conservation	1	2	2	4	3	3
	exposure	1	4	1	0	2	0
	feeding	1	5	3	1	3	1
software	physiology	1	1	1	0	1	0
	physiology	1	1	1	0	1	0
	biodiversity & biogeography	1	1	1	1	0	1
software	connectivity	1	1	1	1	0	1
	physiology	1	1	1	0	1	0

Data products - ATLAS published a total of 177 data products in 2016-2020, and an additional 30 are currently in preparation. They are available in open access on the ATLAS GeoNode². In the present report, we characterised data products according to their data type, main research topic, parameters, methods, geographic region and format. Table 2 provides an overview of the different data types, research topics and parameter types addressed by ATLAS data products. The portfolio is dominated by dynamic maps (raster or vector) of modelled habitat suitability at basin-scale, and by static maps (images) of modelled coral dispersion and habitat connectivity at the scale of ATLAS case studies. Environmental maps resulting from physical, biogeochemical and geomorphological models also predominate. A number of maps based on geomorphological observations and expert's assessments of conservation status and human activity are also available in various formats. The complete inventory of ATLAS data products is provided in Section 3, including the publication year, the access mode, the URL of each data products on the ATLAS GeoNode, and where applicable the URL pointing to the archive where the data product was published. The inventory is also available in a csv file attached to the present report.

Table 2. Summary of ATLAS data products, i.e. georeferenced maps.

Data type	Research topic	Parameter type	parameters	methods	regions	static maps	dynamic maps
observations	biogeography	biological	1	1	1	1	0
	environmental conditions	biogeochemical	1	1	1	1	1
		geomorphological	7	4	1	2	6
		physical	1	1	1	0	1
	environmental processes	biogeochemical	1	1	1	0	1
human activity	industry	1	2	1	2	0	
modelling	environmental conditions	biogeochemical	4	2	1	4	8
		geomorphological	7	4	6	6	1
		physical	5	14	2	14	6
	environmental processes	biogeochemical	1	2	1	2	2
	habitat suitability	biological	12	4	1	0	48
	habitat distribution	ecological	1	1	5	5	0
experts assessment	connectivity	biological	1	4	13	42	4
	conservation	status	4	2	2	0	4
		industry	5	5	3	3	4
human activity	research	2	3	3	4	1	

² <http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/>

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		CO Confidential restricted under conditions set out in Model Grant Agreement		
		CI Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC		

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2 Detailed inventory of ATLAS Data sets

This section provides the complete inventory of ATLAS data sets, characterised according to their data type, main research topic, parameters, methods, geographic region, publication year, access mode, data repository and the URL pointing to each data set. The inventory is also available in a csv file attached to the present report.

Data type	Research topic	Parameter type	Parameter name	Methods	Geographic region	Publication year	Access mode	Data repository	Access to the data sets on the repository (URL)		
observations	ecotoxicology	biological & chemical	microplastic, microfiber, megafauna (4 taxa)	images	ATLAS Case Study 4 (Mingulay Reef)	2019	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.897250		
	morphology	biological	Reteporella (Bryozoa, Cheilostomata)	electron microscopy	ATLAS Case Study 7	2018	open access	zenodo	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1158178		
						2018	open access	zenodo	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1158180		
						2018	open access	zenodo	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1158182		
						2018	open access	zenodo	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1158184		
	species richness	biological	Octocorallia	literature review	ATLAS Case Study 8 (Azores)	2018	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.889711		
	biodiversity & biogeography	biological	megafauna (9 taxa)	in situ benthic image transect	ATLAS Case Study 10 (Davis Strait)	2018	open access	mendeley	http://dx.doi.org/10.17632/cr3xvztwrj.3		
						genetic analysis	North Atlantic Ocean	2020	in prep.	ENA	not yet deposited
								2021	in prep.	ENA	not yet deposited
								2020	in prep.	ENA	not yet deposited
								2021	in prep.	ENA	not yet deposited
								2021	in prep.	ENA	not yet deposited
								2019	open access	ENA	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB33873
2019	open access	seano	https://doi.org/10.12770/0b5d250b-8418-4dda-b39c-960c4481df93								

Data type	Research topic	Parameter type	Parameter name	Methods	Geographic region	Publication year	Access mode	Data repository	Access to the data sets on the repository (URL)
observations	biodiversity & biogeography	biological	<i>Pennatulaceans</i>	EU NAFO groundfish surveys	ATLAS Case Study 11 (Flemish Cap)	2020	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.911150
			<i>Porifera, Pennatulacea, Alcyonacea</i>			2020	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.911147
			<i>Reteporella (Bryozoa, Cheilostomata)</i>	map	ATLAS Case Study 7	2018	open access	zenodo	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1158177
			<i>Swiftia phaeton sp.</i>	video transects	Mauritanian slope	2020	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910893
			peracarid crustaceans	not-provided	Northwest Atlantic Ocean	2019	open access	figshare	https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.8309408.v1
			sponges	a total of 2026 sponge specimens were collected in the field, examined in the laboratory	ATLAS Case Study 10 (Davis Strait)	2019	open access	mendeley	http://dx.doi.org/10.17632/vb4xvxk86v.1
					video transects	ATLAS Case Study 2 (Faroe-Shetland)	2019	in review	pangaea
				ATLAS Case Study 7		2020	in prep.	pangaea	not yet deposited
			megafauna	video transects	ATLAS Case Study 2 (Faroe-Shetland)	2020	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.911023
						2019	in review	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.897592
	ATLAS Case Study 3 (Rockall Bank)	2019			open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.909118		
	paleoceanography	biogeochemical	silt	sediment core	Northwest Atlantic Ocean	2019	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.902454
						2019	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.902449
			spheroidal carbonaceous particle	sediment core	Northwest Atlantic Ocean	2019	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.902471
						2019	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.902469
2019						open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.902468	
2019						open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.902465	

Data type	Research topic	Parameter type	Parameter name	Methods	Geographic region	Publication year	Access mode	Data repository	Access to the data sets on the repository (URL)
observations	paleoceanography	biological	foraminifera	gravity corer	ATLAS Case Study 12 (mid-Atlantic canyons)	2019	in review	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.908480
					Mediterranean Sea	2019	in review	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.908595
		biological	<i>Neogloboquadrina pachyderma</i>	sediment core	Northwest Atlantic Ocean	2019	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.902463
						2019	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.902462
						2019	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.902461
						2019	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.902460
		biological & chemical	foraminifera, Mg/Ca ratio, salinity and d18O	gravity corer	ATLAS Case Study 12 (mid-Atlantic canyons)	2019	in review	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.908479
						2019	in review	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.908478
						2019	in review	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.908477
						2019	in review	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.908476
	2019					in review	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.908470	
	environmental conditions	physical	hydrography and current velocity	CTD and LADCP	ATLAS Case Study 7	2020	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.911408
						2020	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.911405
						2020	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.911404
					ATLAS Case Study 8 (Azores)	2020	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.911406

Data type	Research topic	Parameter type	Parameter name	Methods	Geographic region	Publication year	Access mode	Data repository	Access to the data sets on the repository (URL)
observations	environmental conditions	physical & biogeochemical	environmental drivers	not-provided	Northwest Atlantic Ocean	2019	open access	figshare	https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.10120151.v1
			temperature, salinity, meteorology, dissolved oxygen, nutrients, carbon & trace metals	2016 Extended Ellett Line cruise	ATLAS Case Study 3 (Rockall Bank)	2017	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.881182
						2017	open access	BODC	https://www.bodc.ac.uk/resources/inventories/cruise_inventory/report/16032/
		dissolved oxygen, pH, Total Alkalinity, carbonate ion concentration, dissolved inorganic carbon, and inorganic nutrients (nitrate, nitrite, silicate and phosphate)	CTD	ATLAS Case Study 7 & ATLAS Case Study 8 (Azores)	2018	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.890197	
		geomorphological	lithology (sediment type & colour) & biota	box corer and Van-Veen sampler	ATLAS Case Study 7 & ATLAS Case Study 8 (Azores)	2018	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.889083
			<i>Lophelia</i> thicket, <i>Lophelia</i> framework, coral rubble, lithified hardground, fine sediments with pebbles, cobbles, and boulders (<100 cm diameter), mixed sediment with large boulders (>100 cm), and fine sediments	video transects	ATLAS Case Study 3 (Rockall Bank)	2019	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.909117
			bathymetry	using a Hydrosweep DS-3 multi beam echosounder	ATLAS Case Study 7	2020	in prep.	pangaea	not yet deposited
		ATLAS Case Study 8 (Azores)			2018	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.890073	
					2018	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.890072	
	environmental processes	physical & biogeochemical	hydrography and particle flux	fixed long-term mooring	ATLAS Case Study 3 (Rockall Bank)	2020	in review	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.911033
			transport	time series		2020	open access	BODC	https://cloud.emodnet-ingestion.eu/index.php/s/D8HWQdXjSE98kBJ/

Data type	Research topic	Parameter type	Parameter name	Methods	Geographic region	Publication year	Access mode	Data repository	Access to the data sets on the repository (URL)
observations	environmental processes	physical & biogeochemical	oxygen and nitrogen fluxes	non-invasive in situ aquatic eddy co-variance (AEC) technique, and ex situ whole box core (BC) incubations	ATLAS Case Study 3 (Rockall Bank)	2020	in review	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.911412
	human activity	industry	fishing effort	VMS data	Northwest Atlantic Ocean	2018	open access	DFO	https://open.canada.ca/data/en/dataset/273df20a-47ae-42c0-bc58-01e451d4897a
		research	location of bottom trawls	EU NAFO groundfish surveys	ATLAS Case Study 11 (Flemish Cap)	2020	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.911151
			ship track	RV Sarmiento de Gamboa	ATLAS Case Study 7	2018	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.890074
		society	knowledge & valuation	survey	Canada	2020	embargo (2022.05.01)	zenodo	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3598298
					Norway	2020	embargo (2022.05.01)	zenodo	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3598301
						2019	embargo (2022.05.01)	zenodo	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3598284
					Scotland	2020	embargo (2022.05.01)	zenodo	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3598266
		2020	embargo (2022.05.01)	zenodo		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3598305			
	modelling	connectivity	biological	coral larvae	biologically realistic Lagrangian dispersal model	North Atlantic Ocean	2019	open access	zenodo
using VIKING20, a 1/20th degree ocean model, forced by a hindcast simulation of the atmosphere					2020		open access	zenodo	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3727170
biodiversity & biogeography		biological	corals and sponges	random forest (RF) machine learning approach was used to predict the probability of occurrence and biomass of sponges, sea pens, and large and small gorgonian corals	ATLAS Case Study 10 (Davis Strait)	2019	open access	mendeley	http://dx.doi.org/10.17632/mcb726kcbx.1
				Porifera, Pennatulacea, Alcyonacea	using kernel density estimation to create a modelled biomass	ATLAS Case Study 11 (Flemish Cap)	2018	open access	mendeley
environmental processes		biogeochemical	particulate organic carbon (POC) flux	all predictor variables were projected with the Albers equal-area conical projection centred in the middle of the study area	North Atlantic Ocean	2020	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.911117
			net primary production (NPP)	ArcGIS format	ATLAS Case Study 8 (Azores)	2017	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.872601
			corals, organic carbon deposition rates (mmol C m ⁻² d ⁻¹)	using the suitability model of Rengstorf et al.	ATLAS Case Study 3 (Rockall Bank)	2020	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.911414

Data type	Research topic	Parameter type	Parameter name	Methods	Geographic region	Publication year	Access mode	Data repository	Access to the data sets on the repository (URL)
modelling	environmental conditions	geomorphological	abyssal, littoral, lower bathyal, middle bathyal, upper bathyal, and upper slope zones	ArcGIS format	ATLAS Case Study 8 (Azores)	2016	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.862152
		physical	density	not-provided	ATLAS Case Study 10 (Davis Strait)	2019	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.902456
			temperature, salinity	not-provided		2019	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.902459
			temperature	not-provided	North Atlantic Ocean	2019	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.902492
			temperature, AMOC	not-provided		2019	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.902494
			temperature, salinity, currents, sea surface height	includes all computational grids, initialization fields and boundary conditions for each case study area	ATLAS Case Study 3 (Rockall Bank)	2019	open access	zenodo	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3582932
		ATLAS Case Study 8 (Azores)			2019	open access	zenodo	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3582932	
		physical & biogeochemical	sea surface temperature (SST) and chlorophyll a	ArcGIS format	ATLAS Case Study 8 (Azores)	2017	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.872601
			not-provided	data layers collected over different spatial scales and temporal resolutions were interpolated using ordinary kriging methods	ATLAS Case Study 11 (Flemish Cap)	2019	open access	mendeley	http://dx.doi.org/10.17632/zmwyjs222s.2
			temperature, pH, oxygen, aragonite, calcite	all predictor variables were projected with the Albers equal-area conical projection centred in the middle of the study area	North Atlantic Ocean	2020	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.911117
	habitat suitability	biological	corals and sponges	using Kernel Density Analyses and Species Distribution Models	ATLAS Case Study 11 (Flemish Cap)	2018	open access	mendeley	http://dx.doi.org/10.17632/hnp4xr2sy3.1
			12 taxa	using an ensemble modelling approach employing three widely-used modelling methods: the Maxent maximum entropy model, Generalized Additive Models, and Random Forest	North Atlantic Ocean	2019	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
	conservation	status	vulnerable marine ecosystems	not-provided	North Atlantic Ocean	2019	open access	seanoe	https://www.seanoe.org/data/00514/62541/
	paleoceanography	chemical	Pb 210 activity	gravity corer	Northwest Atlantic Ocean	2019	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.902490
2019						open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.902489	

Data type	Research topic	Parameter type	Parameter name	Methods	Geographic region	Publication year	Access mode	Data repository	Access to the data sets on the repository (URL)
modelling	paleoceanography	time	age	age and SPG UOHC in 0 - 700 m	Northwest Atlantic Ocean	2019	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.902491
				age model		2019	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.902486
						2019	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.902483
						2019	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.902481
						2019	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.902476
				alternate binning ages (year CE)		2019	open access	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.902493
expert's assessment	conservation	status	vulnerable marine ecosystems	VME habitats and VME indicators	ATLAS Case Study 8 (Azores)	2019	open access	ICES	https://www.ices.dk/marine-data/data-portals/Pages/vulnerable-marine-ecosystems.aspx
						2019	open access	ICES	https://www.ices.dk/marine-data/data-portals/Pages/vulnerable-marine-ecosystems.aspx
						2019	open access	ICES	https://www.ices.dk/marine-data/data-portals/Pages/vulnerable-marine-ecosystems.aspx
			good environmental status	not-provided	North Atlantic Ocean	2020	in review	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.911409
				shapefiles	ATLAS Case Study 2 (Faroe-Shetland)	2020	in review	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.911157
					ATLAS Case Study 4 (Mingulay Reef)	2020	in review	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.911163
experiments	exposure	biological & chemical	<i>Halichondria panicea, Benzo-A-Pyrene</i>	time series laboratory incubation	not-provided	2020	in review	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.911441
			<i>Halichondria panicea, hydrocarbon</i>			2020	in review	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.911443
	feeding	biological	<i>antipatharian</i>	laboratory experiment	ATLAS Case Study 8 (Azores)	2020	embargo (2021.05.01)	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.913195
			<i>Dentomuricea aff. Meteor, Viminella flagellum</i>	laboratory experiments zooplankton capture rates		2020	embargo (2021.05.01)	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.913194
			octocorals	laboratory experiment		2020	embargo (2021.05.01)	pangaea	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.913184
			<i>Lophelia, Hymedesmia</i>	assessed with isotopically-enriched particulate food sources	not-provided	2018	open access	zenodo	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1198189

Data type	Research topic	Parameter type	Parameter name	Methods	Geographic region	Publication year	Access mode	Data repository	Access to the data sets on the repository (URL)
	physiology	biological	biota	not-provided	not-provided	2020	in prep.	pangaea	not yet deposited
software	biodiversity & biogeography	biological	microbiome	genetic analysis	North Atlantic Ocean	2019	open access	ifremer	https://gitlab.ifremer.fr/abyss-project/
	connectivity		coral larvae	biologically realistic Lagrangian dispersal model		2020	open access	zenodo	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3754103
	physiology		biota	laboratory experiment	not-provided	2020	in prep.	zenodo	not yet deposited

3 Detailed inventory of ATLAS Data products (geographic information layers)

This section provides the complete inventory of ATLAS data products, characterised according to their data type, main research topic, parameters, methods, geographic region, format, publication year, URL pointing to each data product on ATLAS GeoNode, and where applicable the URL pointing to the archive where the data product was published. Data formats are the following: static image (jpg), vector data (PNG, PDF, JPEG), raster data (GeoTIFF, GZIP, PNG, PDF, JPEG). The inventory is also available in a csv file attached to the present report.

Data type	Research topic	Parameter type	Parameter name	Methods	Geographic region	Data format	Publication year	GeoNode URL	Archive URL			
observations	biogeography	biological	Lophelia pertusa	obtained from the MAREANO's map service	ATLAS Case Study 1 (LoVe Observatory)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/70	not-provided			
	environmental conditions	biogeochemical	chlorophyll a	present-day (2003-2013) range with a spatial resolution of 4km and units mg/m3	ATLAS Case Study 8 (Azores)	raster data	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:ChlorophyllRange	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.872601			
						static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/116	https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.872601			
			geomorphological	canyons	plateaus	ridges	aggregated from available sources	ATLAS Case Study 8 (Azores)	vector data	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:canyons_azores	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.862152
									vector data	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:plateaus_azores	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.862152
									vector data	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:ridges_azores	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.862152
									vector data	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:rifit_valleys_azores	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.862152
									vector data	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:rises_azores	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.862152
									vector data	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:rises_azores	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.862152
			rock-, mud-, sand- or coarse-sediments, mixed sediments, sandy mud and muddy sand	aggregated from multibeam backscatter and seismic surveys, point data digitized from up-to-date and historical nautical charts for the Azores, and data provided by the World Seabed Data Browser	ATLAS Case Study 8 (Azores)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/113	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.862152			
						vector data	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Seabed_Az0	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.862152			

Data type	Research topic	Parameter type	Parameter name	Methods	Geographic region	Data format	Publication year	GeoNode URL	Archive URL
observations	environmental conditions	geomorphological	sublittoral, upper slope, upper bathyal, mid bathyal, lower bathyal, and abyssal	SRTM30_PLUS was used to delimit the depth-based biological zones proposed by Howell (2010)	ATLAS Case Study 8 (Azores)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/34	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.862152
		physical	sea surface temperature (SST)	present-day (2003-2013) mean, obtained from remote sensing products	ATLAS Case Study 8 (Azores)	raster data	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:sst_mean_03_13	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.872601
	environmental processes	biogeochemical	net primary production (NPP)	present-day (2003-2013) mean, obtained from remote sensing products	ATLAS Case Study 8 (Azores)	raster data	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:npp_mean03_13	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.872601
	human activity	industry	demersal fisheries	Vessel Monitoring System (VMS) location and identity of all UK registered commercial fishing vessels greater than 15 m in length and using mobile gear during 2009-2013. Observations are anonymised and aggregated.	ATLAS Case Study 2 (Faroe-Shetland)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/189	not-provided
				Vessel Monitoring System (VMS) location and identity of all UK registered commercial fishing vessels greater than 15 m in length and using static gear during 2009-2013. Observations are anonymised and aggregated.		static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/190	not-provided
	modelling	environmental conditions	biogeochemical	bottom water dissolved oxygen concentration	near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5)	North Atlantic Ocean	raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Oxy_FromKrige_3km_2081_2100
recent-past (1951-2000), present-day					raster data		2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Oxy_FromKrige_3km_1951_2000	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.911117
near seafloor aragonite saturation				near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5)	North Atlantic Ocean	raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Arag_FromKrige_3km_2081_2100	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.911117
				recent-past (1951-2000), present-day	North Atlantic Ocean	static image	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/506	https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.911117
near seafloor aragonite saturation			recent-past (1951-2000), present-day	North Atlantic Ocean	raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Arag_FromKrige_3km_1951_20000	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.911117	
					static image	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/503	https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.911117	

Data type	Research topic	Parameter type	Parameter name	Methods	Geographic region	Data format	Publication year	GeoNode URL	Archive URL		
modelling	environmental conditions	biogeochemical	near seafloor calcite saturation	near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5)	North Atlantic Ocean	raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Calc_FromKrige_3km_2081_2100	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.911117		
				static image	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/507	https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.911117				
				recent-past (1951-2000), present-day	North Atlantic Ocean	raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Calc_FromKrige_3km_1951_2000	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.911117		
				static image	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/505	https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.911117				
			pH	near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5)	North Atlantic Ocean	raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:ph_FromKrige_3km_2081_2100	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.911117		
				recent-past (1951-2000), present-day	North Atlantic Ocean	raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:ph_FromKrige_3km_1951_2000	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.911117		
				geomorphological	bathymetry	global terrain model for ocean at 30 arc-second intervals, largely based on a database of ship-track soundings with interpolation between soundings guided by satellite-derived gravity data	ATLAS Case Study 2 (Faroe-Shetland)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/188	https://doi.org/10.5285/836f016a-33be-6ddc-e053-6c86abc0788e
						ATLAS Case Study 3 (Rockall Bank)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/195	https://doi.org/10.5285/836f016a-33be-6ddc-e053-6c86abc0788e	
		ATLAS Case Study 8 (Azores)	static image			2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/114	https://doi.org/10.5285/836f016a-33be-6ddc-e053-6c86abc0788e			
		ATLAS Case Study 9 (Reykjanes Ridge)	static image			2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/216	https://doi.org/10.5285/836f016a-33be-6ddc-e053-6c86abc0788e			
		North Atlantic Ocean	static image			2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/23	https://doi.org/10.5285/836f016a-33be-6ddc-e053-6c86abc0788e			
		obtained from the Norwegian Mapping Authority Hydrographic Service	ATLAS Case Study 1 (LoVe Observatory)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/179	not-provided				
		abyssal zone	SRTM30_PLUS was used to delimit the depth-based biological zones proposed by Howell (2010)	ATLAS Case Study 8 (Azores)	vector data	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Abyssal0	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.862152			

Data type	Research topic	Parameter type	Parameter name	Methods	Geographic region	Data format	Publication year	GeoNode URL	Archive URL
modelling	environmental conditions	geomorphological	littoral zone	SRTM30_PLUS was used to delimit the depth-based biological zones proposed by Howell (2010)	ATLAS Case Study 8 (Azores)	vector data	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Littoral_200m	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.862152
			lower bathyal zone			vector data	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Lower_bathyal	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.862152
			middle bathyal zone			vector data	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Mid_bathyal	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.862152
			upper bathyal zone			vector data	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Upper_bathyal	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.862152
			upper slope			vector data	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Upper_slope	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.862152
		physical	mixed layer depth (m)	recent-past (1959-2009) seasonal statistics from the VIKING20 model	ATLAS Case Studies (all)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/419	not-provided
						vector data	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:SeasonalCycle_MLDO	not-provided
			near-bottom eddy kinetic energy (x10 ⁻² m ² s ⁻²)	1959-2009 eddy kinetic energy from the deepest depth bin at each grid point in output from the Viking20 model. 1959-2009 mean kinetic energy from the deepest depth bin at each grid point in output from the Viking20 model. Kinetic energy is defined $u^2 + v^2$ where u and v are the horizontal velocities.	North Atlantic Ocean	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/392	not-provided
						static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/391	not-provided
			near-bottom potential temperature (deg C)	1959-2009 mean bottom potential temperature from the deepest depth bin at each grid point in output from the Viking20 model.	North Atlantic Ocean	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/389	not-provided
				1959-2009 standard deviation of potential temperature from the deepest depth bin at each grid point in output from the Viking20 model. The standard deviation is plotted on a log10 scale to resolve changes across all depths.		static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/390	not-provided
				1959-2017 mean potential temperature from the deepest depth bin at each grid point in the EN4 objectively analysed dataset.		static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/385	https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/hadobs/en4/
				1959-2017 standard deviation of potential temperature from the deepest depth bin at each grid point in the EN4 objectively analysed dataset. The standard deviation is plotted on a log10 scale to resolve changes across all depths.		static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/386	https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/hadobs/en4/

Data type	Research topic	Parameter type	Parameter name	Methods	Geographic region	Data format	Publication year	GeoNode URL	Archive URL
modelling	environmental conditions	physical	near-bottom potential temperature (deg C)	near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5)	North Atlantic Ocean	raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Temp_FromKrige_3km_2081_21000	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.911117
				recent-past (1951-2000), present-day		raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Temp_FromKrige_3km_1951_20000	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.911117
				recent-past (1959-2009) seasonal statistics from the VIKING20 model	ATLAS Case Studies (all)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/421	not-provided
			vector data			2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:SeasonalCycle_Tbot6	not-provided	
			near-bottom salinity (psu)	North Atlantic Ocean	1959-2009 mean salinity from the deepest depth bin at each grid point in output from the Viking20 model.	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/387	not-provided
					1959-2009 standard deviation of salinity from the deepest depth bin at each grid point in output from the Viking20 model. The standard deviation is plotted on a log10 scale to resolve changes across all depths.	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/388	not-provided
		1959-2017 mean salinity from the deepest depth bin at each grid point in the EN4 objectively analysed dataset.			static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/383	https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/hadobs/en4/	
		1959-2017 standard deviation of salinity from the deepest depth bin at each grid point in the EN4 objectively analysed dataset. The standard deviation is plotted on a log10 scale to resolve changes across all depths.			static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/384	https://www.metoffice.gov.uk/hadobs/en4/	
		recent-past (1959-2009) seasonal statistics from the VIKING20 model		ATLAS Case Studies (all)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/422	not-provided	
					vector data	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:SeasonalCycle_Sbot0	not-provided	
		sea surface temperature (deg C)	ATLAS Case Studies (all)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/420	not-provided		
				vector data	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:SeasonalCycle_SST1	not-provided		

Data type	Research topic	Parameter type	Parameter name	Methods	Geographic region	Data format	Publication year	GeoNode URL	Archive URL
modelling	environmental processes	biogeochemical	particulate organic carbon (POC) flux at 100 m depth (epc100)	near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5)	North Atlantic Ocean	raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:epc_from_krige_3km_2081_2100	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.911117
				static image		2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/511	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.911117	
				recent-past (1951-2000), present-day	North Atlantic Ocean	raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Epc_FromKrige_3km_1951_20000	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.911117
				static image		2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/512	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.911117	
	habitat suitability	biological	<i>Acanella arbuscula</i>	near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5). An ensemble modelling approach was used.	North Atlantic Ocean	raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Acanella_arbuscula_HSI_Ensemble_fut	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
				near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5). An ensemble modelling approach was used with maximum sensitivity and specificity with a 10-percentile training presence threshold		raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Acanella_arbuscula_GainLossRef_10th	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
				near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5). An ensemble modelling approach was used with maximum sensitivity and specificity.		raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Acanella_arbuscula_GainLossRef_MSS	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
				recent-past (1951-2000), present-day. An ensemble modelling approach was used.		raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Acanella_arbuscula_HSI_Ensemble_pres	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
			<i>Acanthogorgia armata</i>	near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5). An ensemble modelling approach was used.	North Atlantic Ocean	raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Acanthogorgia_armata_HSI_Ensemble_fut	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
				near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5). An ensemble modelling approach was used with maximum sensitivity and specificity with a 10-percentile training presence threshold		raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Acanthogorgia_armata_GainLossRef_10th	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
				near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5). An ensemble modelling approach was used with maximum sensitivity and specificity.		raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Acanthogorgia_armata_GainLossRef_MSS	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
				recent-past (1951-2000), present-day. An ensemble modelling approach was used.		raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Acanthogorgia_armata_HSI_Ensemble_pres	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319

Data type	Research topic	Parameter type	Parameter name	Methods	Geographic region	Data format	Publication year	GeoNode URL	Archive URL
modelling	habitat suitability	biologica	<i>Coryphaenoides rupestris</i>	near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5). An ensemble modelling approach was used.	North Atlantic Ocean	raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Coryphaenoides_rupestris_HSI_Ensemble_fut	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
				near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5). An ensemble modelling approach was used with maximum sensitivity and specificity with a 10-percentile training presence threshold		raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Coryphaenoides_rupestris_GainLossRef_10th	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
				near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5). An ensemble modelling approach was used with maximum sensitivity and specificity.		raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Coryphaenoides_rupestris_GainLossRef_MSS	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
				recent-past (1951-2000), present-day. An ensemble modelling approach was used.		raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Coryphaenoides_rupestris_HSI_Ensemble_pres	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
			<i>Desmophyllum dianthus</i>	near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5). An ensemble modelling approach was used.	North Atlantic Ocean	raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Desmophyllum_dianthus_HSI_Ensemble_fut	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
				near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5). An ensemble modelling approach was used with maximum sensitivity and specificity with a 10-percentile training presence threshold		raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Desmophyllum_dianthus_GainLossRef_10th	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
				near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5). An ensemble modelling approach was used with maximum sensitivity and specificity.		raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Desmophyllum_dianthus_GainLossRef_MSS	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
				recent-past (1951-2000), present-day. An ensemble modelling approach was used.		raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Desmophyllum_dianthus_HSI_Ensemble_pres	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
			<i>Gadus morhua</i>	near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5). An ensemble modelling approach was used.	North Atlantic Ocean	raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Gadus_morhua_HSI_Ensemble_fut	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
				near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5). An ensemble modelling approach was used with maximum sensitivity and specificity with a 10-percentile training presence threshold		raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Gadus_morhua_GainLossRef_10th	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
				near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5). An ensemble modelling approach was used with maximum sensitivity and specificity.		raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Gadus_morhua_GainLossRef_MSS	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
				recent-past (1951-2000), present-day. An ensemble modelling approach was used.		raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Gadus_morhua_HSI_Ensemble_pres	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319

Data type	Research topic	Parameter type	Parameter name	Methods	Geographic region	Data format	Publication year	GeoNode URL	Archive URL
modelling	habitat suitability	biological	<i>Helicolenus dactylopterus</i>	near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5). An ensemble modelling approach was used.	North Atlantic Ocean	raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Helicolenus_dactylopterus_HSI_Ensemble_fut	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
				near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5). An ensemble modelling approach was used with maximum sensitivity and specificity with a 10-percentile training presence threshold		raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Helicolenus_dactylopterus_GainLossRef_10th	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
				near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5). An ensemble modelling approach was used with maximum sensitivity and specificity.		raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Helicolenus_dactylopterus_GainLossRef_MSS	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
				recent-past (1951-2000), present-day. An ensemble modelling approach was used.		raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Helicolenus_dactylopterus_HSI_Ensemble_pres	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
			<i>Hippoglossoides platessoides</i>	near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5). An ensemble modelling approach was used.	North Atlantic Ocean	raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Hippoglossoides_platessoides_HSI_Ensemble_fut	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
				near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5). An ensemble modelling approach was used with maximum sensitivity and specificity with a 10-percentile training presence threshold		raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Hippoglossoides_platessoides_GainLossRef_10th	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
				near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5). An ensemble modelling approach was used with maximum sensitivity and specificity.		raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Hippoglossoides_platessoides_GainLossRef_MSS	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
				recent-past (1951-2000), present-day. An ensemble modelling approach was used.		raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Hippoglossoides_platessoides_HSI_Ensemble_pres	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
			<i>Lophelia pertusa</i>	near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5). An ensemble modelling approach was used.	North Atlantic Ocean	raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Lophelia_pertusa_HSI_Ensemble_fut	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
				near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5). An ensemble modelling approach was used with maximum sensitivity and specificity with a 10-percentile training presence threshold		raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Lophelia_pertusa_GainLossRef_10th	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
				near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5). An ensemble modelling approach was used with maximum sensitivity and specificity.		raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Lophelia_pertusa_GainLossRef_MSS	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
				recent-past (1951-2000), present-day. An ensemble modelling approach was used.		raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Lophelia_pertusa_HSI_Ensemble_pres	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319

Data type	Research topic	Parameter type	Parameter name	Methods	Geographic region	Data format	Publication year	GeoNode URL	Archive URL
modelling	habitat suitability	biological	<i>Madrepora oculata</i>	near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5). An ensemble modelling approach was used.	North Atlantic Ocean	raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Madrepora_oculata_HSI_Ensemble_fut	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
				near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5). An ensemble modelling approach was used with maximum sensitivity and specificity with a 10-percentile training presence threshold		raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Madrepora_oculata_GainLossRef_10th	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
				near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5). An ensemble modelling approach was used with maximum sensitivity and specificity.		raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Madrepora_oculata_GainLossRef_MSS	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
				recent-past (1951-2000), present-day. An ensemble modelling approach was used.		raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Madrepora_oculata_HSI_Ensemble_pres	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
			<i>Paragorgia arborea</i>	near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5). An ensemble modelling approach was used.	North Atlantic Ocean	raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Paragorgia_arborea_HSI_Ensemble_fut	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
				near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5). An ensemble modelling approach was used with maximum sensitivity and specificity with a 10-percentile training presence threshold		raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Paragorgia_arborea_GainLossRef_10th	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
				near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5). An ensemble modelling approach was used with maximum sensitivity and specificity.		raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Paragorgia_arborea_GainLossRef_MSS	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
				recent-past (1951-2000), present-day. An ensemble modelling approach was used.		raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Paragorgia_arborea_HSI_Ensemble_pres	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
			<i>Reinhardtius hippoglossoides</i>	near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5). An ensemble modelling approach was used.	North Atlantic Ocean	raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Reinhardtius_hippoglossoides_HSI_Ensemble_fut	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
				near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5). An ensemble modelling approach was used with maximum sensitivity and specificity with a 10-percentile training presence threshold		raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Reinhardtius_hippoglossoides_GainLossRef_10th	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
				near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5). An ensemble modelling approach was used with maximum sensitivity and specificity.		raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Reinhardtius_hippoglossoides_GainLossRef_MSS	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
				recent-past (1951-2000), present-day. An ensemble modelling approach was used.		raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Reinhardtius_hippoglossoides_HSI_Ensemble_pres	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319

Data type	Research topic	Parameter type	Parameter name	Methods	Geographic region	Data format	Publication year	GeoNode URL	Archive URL
modelling	habitat suitability	biological	<i>Sebastes mentella</i>	near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5). An ensemble modelling approach was used.	North Atlantic Ocean	raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Sebastes_mentella_HSI_Ensemble_fut	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
				near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5). An ensemble modelling approach was used with maximum sensitivity and specificity with a 10-percentile training presence threshold		raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Sebastes_mentella_GainLossRef_10th	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
				near-future (2081-2100) using the high-end of possible baseline emissions scenarios (RCP8.5). An ensemble modelling approach was used with maximum sensitivity and specificity.		raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Sebastes_mentella_GainLossRef_MSS	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
				recent-past (1951-2000), present-day. An ensemble modelling approach was used.		raster data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:Sebastes_mentella_HSI_Ensemble_pres	https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.910319
	habitat distribution	ecological	EUNIS and MSFD habitat classification	observation-driven, predicted distributions by EUSeaMap 2016	ATLAS Case Studies (European)	static image	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/499	http://gis.ices.dk/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/01bf1f24-fdcc-4ee7-af8b-e62cf72fe2f9
					ATLAS Case Studies 3-6	static image	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/500	http://gis.ices.dk/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/01bf1f24-fdcc-4ee7-af8b-e62cf72fe2f9
					ATLAS Case Study 1 (LoVe Observatory)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/180	http://gis.ices.dk/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/01bf1f24-fdcc-4ee7-af8b-e62cf72fe2f9
					ATLAS Case Study 2 (Faroe-Shetland)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/192	http://gis.ices.dk/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/01bf1f24-fdcc-4ee7-af8b-e62cf72fe2f9
					ATLAS Case Study 9 (Reykjanes Ridge)	static image	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/502	http://gis.ices.dk/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/01bf1f24-fdcc-4ee7-af8b-e62cf72fe2f9
	connectivity	biological	coral larvae	dispersion across 25km x 25km spatial units under a "20 days PLD" scenario, using 30 solutions of combined biological traits and the VIKING20 circulation model	ATLAS Case Study 1 (LoVe Observatory)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/352	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541
					ATLAS Case Study 7 (Gulf of Cádiz)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/213	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541
					ATLAS Case Study 8 (Azores)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/211	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541

Data type	Research topic	Parameter type	Parameter name	Methods	Geographic region	Data format	Publication year	GeoNode URL	Archive URL
modelling	connectivity	Biological	coral larvae	dispersion across 25km x 25km spatial units under a "20 days PLD" scenario, using 30 solutions of combined biological traits and the VIKING20 circulation model	ATLAS Case Study 9 (Reykjanes Ridge)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/210	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541
					ATLAS Case Study 2 (Faroe-Shetland)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/287	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541
					ATLAS Case Study 3 (Rockall Bank)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/215	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541
					ATLAS Case Study 4 (Mingulay Reef)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/351	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541
					ATLAS Case Study 5 (Southwest of Ireland)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/212	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541
					ATLAS Case Study 6 (Bay of Biscay)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/208	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541
					ATLAS Case Study 10 (Davis Strait)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/286	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541
					ATLAS Case Study 11 (Flemish Cap)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/214	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541
					ATLAS Case Study 12 (mid-Atlantic canyons)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/285	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541
					North Atlantic Ocean	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/353	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541
				vector data		2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:connectivity_PLD20_SelFreq0	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541	
				dispersion across 25km x 25km spatial units under a "all benthic regionalisation" scenario, using 30 solutions of combined biological traits and the VIKING20 circulation model	ATLAS Case Study 1 (LoVe Observatory)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/357	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541
					ATLAS Case Study 4 (Mingulay Reef)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/358	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541

Data type	Research topic	Parameter type	Parameter name	Methods	Geographic region	Data format	Publication year	GeoNode URL	Archive URL			
modelling	connectivity	Biological	coral larvae	dispersion across 25km x 25km spatial units under a "all benthic regionalisation" scenario, using 30 solutions of combined biological traits and the VIKING20 circulation model	North Atlantic Ocean	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/356	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541			
					North Atlantic Ocean	vector data	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:benthicfeatures_regional_SelfReq	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541			
								ATLAS Case Study 1 (LoVe Observatory)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/288	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541
								ATLAS Case Study 7 (Gulf of Cádiz)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/293	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541
								ATLAS Case Study 8 (Azores)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/294	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541
								ATLAS Case Study 9 (Reykjanes Ridge)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/295	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541
							dispersion across 25km x 25km spatial units under a "all features" scenario, using 30 solutions of combined biological traits and the VIKING20 circulation model	ATLAS Case Study 2 (Faroe-Shetland)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/289	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541
								ATLAS Case Study 3 (Rockall Bank)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/290	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541
								ATLAS Case Study 4 (Mingulay Reef)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/349	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541
								ATLAS Case Study 5 (Southwest of Ireland)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/291	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541
								ATLAS Case Study 6 (Bay of Biscay)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/292	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541
								ATLAS Case Study 10 (Davis Strait)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/296	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541
			ATLAS Case Study 11 (Flemish Cap)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/297		https://doi.org/10.17882/62541				

Data type	Research topic	Parameter type	Parameter name	Methods	Geographic region	Data format	Publication year	GeoNode URL	Archive URL			
modelling	connectivity	biological	coral larvae	dispersion across 25km x 25km spatial units under a "all features" scenario, using 30 solutions of combined biological traits and the VIKING20 circulation model	ATLAS Case Study 12 (mid-Atlantic canyons)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/298	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541			
					North Atlantic Ocean	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/355	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541			
						vector data	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:allfeatures_regional_SelfFreq0	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541			
							dispersion across 25km x 25km spatial units under a "all management" scenario, using 30 solutions of combined biological traits and the VIKING20 circulation model	ATLAS Case Study 1 (LoVe Observatory)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/312	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541
								ATLAS Case Study 7 (Gulf of Cádiz)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/307	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541
								ATLAS Case Study 8 (Azores)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/306	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541
								ATLAS Case Study 9 (Reykjanes Ridge)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/305	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541
								ATLAS Case Study 2 (Faroe-Shetland)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/311	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541
								ATLAS Case Study 3 (Rockall Bank)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/310	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541
								ATLAS Case Study 4 (Mingulay Reef)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/350	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541
								ATLAS Case Study 5 (Southwest of Ireland)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/309	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541
								ATLAS Case Study 6 (Bay of Biscay)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/308	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541
				ATLAS Case Study 10 (Davis Strait)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/304	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541				

Data type	Research topic	Parameter type	Parameter name	Methods	Geographic region	Data format	Publication year	GeoNode URL	Archive URL
modelling	connectivity	biological	coral larvae	dispersion across 25km x 25km spatial units under a "all management" scenario, using 30 solutions of combined biological traits and the VIKING20 circulation model	ATLAS Case Study 11 (Flemish Cap)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/303	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541
					ATLAS Case Study 12 (mid-Atlantic canyons)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/302	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541
					North Atlantic Ocean	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/354	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541
						vector data	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode/all_management_Selfreq0	https://doi.org/10.17882/62541
expert's assessment	conservation	status	Spatial Assessment Units (SAUs)	using the Nested Environmental status Assessment Tool (NEAT)	ATLAS Case Studies (Europe)	vector data	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:SAUs_All	not-provided
			seamount seabed habitat vulnerability and fisheries closure	present-day areas identified by NAFO as being vulnerable to bottom contact gears, and where no vessel shall engage in bottom fishing activities	ATLAS Case Study 11 (Flemish Cap)	vector data	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:a_2018_Closures_seamounts	https://www.nafo.int/
			sponge & coral seabed habitat vulnerability and fisheries closure			vector data	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:a_2019_Closures_sponge_coral	https://www.nafo.int/
			coral seabed habitat vulnerability and fisheries closure			vector data	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:a_2015_Closures_30	https://www.nafo.int/
	human activity	conservation, industry and research	shipping, undersea cable routes, fisheries, scientific research and hydrocarbon exploration	present-day activity areas obtained from NAFO and C-NLOPB	ATLAS Case Study 11 (Flemish Cap)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/66	https://www.nafo.int/
				present-day areas identified by NAFO as being vulnerable to bottom contact gears, and where no vessel shall engage in bottom fishing activities		static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/47	https://www.nafo.int/

Data type	Research topic	Parameter type	Parameter name	Methods	Geographic region	Data format	Publication year	GeoNode URL	Archive URL
expert's assessment	human activity	Industry	oil and gas activity	near-future, indicative areas identified by the 30th offshore licensing round	UK Exclusive Economic Zone	vector data	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:OGA_30th_Round_Indicative_Areas_WGS84	https://www.ogauthority.co.uk/data-centre/
				near-future, indicative areas identified by the 31st offshore licensing round	UK Exclusive Economic Zone	vector data	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:OGA_31st_Round_Indicative_Areas_WGS84	https://www.ogauthority.co.uk/data-centre/
			oil and gas activity	near-future, indicative areas identified by the Oil and Gas Authority (OGA) during the last three offshore licensing rounds	ATLAS Case Study 2 (Faroe-Shetland)	static image	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/191	https://www.nafo.int/
		industry	oil and gas exploration	present-day offshore licensing areas issued by C-NLOPB who manages the rights issuance processes on behalf of the Government of Canada and the Government of Newfoundland and Labrador	ATLAS Case Study 11 (Flemish Cap)	vector data	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:ExplorationLicences_OilGas	https://www.nafo.int/
			oil and gas production			vector data	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:ProductionLicences_OilGas	https://www.nafo.int/
			oil and gas significant discovery			vector data	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:SignificantDiscoveryLicences_OilGas	https://www.nafo.int/
			case studies			determined for the purpose of H2020 project ATLAS	ATLAS Case Studies (all)	static image	2019
		research	case studies	determined for the purpose of H2020 project ATLAS	ATLAS Case Studies (all)	vector data	2019	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/layers/geonode:ATLAS_CaseStudy_areas	not-provided
						ATLAS Case Studies (Europe)	static image	2020	http://www.atlas-horizon2020.eu/documents/423